

The Safety and Efficacy of Sugammadex in Patients with Chronic Renal Failure

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Background

- Sugammadex (SGX) has been progressively establishing itself as the standard of practice for neuromuscular blockade (NM) antagonism
- 2023 ASA guidelines recommend the use of SGX for shallow, moderate, and deep levels of rocuronium-induced NMB to avoid residual paralysis but do not mention its use in patients with chronic renal failure (CRF)
- FDA & Merck do not recommend the use of SGX in patients with severe renal impairment, including those requiring dialysis

Purpose

The purpose of this project was to examine the literature regarding the safety and efficacy of SGX for reversing rocuronium-induced NMB in adults with chronic renal failure

Methods

- A literature review was conducted under the guidance of the Prisma Statement
- An expert in field was interviewed for unpublished findings and expert opinion

Discussion

- There is not enough data to support the recommended use of SGX in this population
- There are currently no ongoing research studies supported by Merck and there are no plans to pursue a reversal of the FDA's recommendations
- SGX may be a safe and efficacious antagonist of rocuronium-induced NMB in adult patients with severe renal failure

Available Evidence

John Hopkins EBP Hierarchy of Evidence

Findings

Efficacy

- SGX was an effective antagonist of moderate and deep levels of rocuronium-induced NMB but the time to full recovery (TOFr > 0.9) was prolonged in renal patients as compared to normal renal function

Depth of NMB	Dose of SGX (mg/kg)	Mean Recovery Time (min)	
		CrCl < 30 mL/min	CrCl ≥ 80 mL/min
Moderate (T2)	2.0	2.0 ± 0.72	1.65 ± 0.63
Deep (PTC 1-2)	4.0	5.6 ± 3.6	2.7 ± 1.3

Pharmacokinetics

- ↓ Renal function = ↓ plasma clearance & ↑ mean exposure, elimination ½ life, mean resident time
- No SGX detected after 7 days
- Rocuronium detected after 7 days but not after 28 days
- 1st hemodialysis session w/high-flux filters = ↓ 69% SGX and ↓ 75% rocuronium; ↓ ~50% for subsequent sessions

Safety

- No evidence of recurarization during postoperative period of 24-48 hours
- No significant difference in 30-day and 1-year mortality rates in ESRD patients who received sugammadex vs those who did not
- No significant adverse events

Renal Transplantation (rocuronium-SGX vs cisatracurium-neostigmine)

- No increased risk of AKI after transplantation
- ↓ Serum creatinine & urea levels 24 hr post-transplant
- ↓ Incidences of postoperative severe hypoxemia & ICU admissions & shorter PACU stays
- No AEs or signs of NMB recurrence 72 hr post-transplant or at 6 months
- No differences in rejection and 28-day mortality rates

Limitations

- Limited available data at lower levels of evidence
- Small sample sizes in prospective studies

Recommendations

- More robust data are needed for a definitive recommendation
- If used off-label, base decision on best available evidence

Suggestions for Practice

To minimize patient risks during the off-label drug use of SGX in patients with severe renal failure:

- Have an in-depth understanding of both the medication and the patient's medical history
- Have a compelling rationale for administration
- Utilize neuromuscular monitoring
- Follow manufacturer dosing guidelines

Conclusion

- SGX may be a valuable option for the NMB management in patients with severe renal failure
- If SGX is used off-label, providers have the ethical and professional duty to be informed of the current research

References

